

Digital Technologies for Construction Circular Economy

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Abstract:

The construction industry is vital for global economic growth, but it faces the challenge of delivering the built environment efficiently and sustainably. This sector consumes large amounts of raw materials and generates significant waste, with the UK alone producing 138 million tons of construction waste. Transitioning to a circular economy is seen as a crucial approach to address environmental concerns and promote economic growth. To achieve sustainable development goals, the construction sector can adopt Circular Economy (CE) standards. Integrating Construction 4.0 technologies can support this transition by optimizing resource management and enhancing circularity. However, while there is extensive research on digital technologies in construction, there is a lack of focus on integrating these technologies to support circular practices. This paper explores the potential of integrating Industry 4.0 technologies in the construction circular economy, particularly the Reduce, Reuse, Recycle (3R) principles. Technologies such as Building Information Modelling (BIM), Geographic Information System (GIS), Blockchain, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT) are analysed for their role in managing digital information throughout the lifecycle of built asset projects. By conducting a comprehensive literature review, this study aims to contribute to the advancement of circular economy practices in the construction industry. It examines how these technologies enable resource reduction, promote material reuse, and facilitate effective recycling practices. The integration of Industry 4.0 technologies in the construction sector can drive the adoption of circular economy principles and enhance the sector's sustainability.

Keywords: Construction and Demolition Waste Management, Industry 4.0, Construction Circular Economy, Building Information Modelling